

Terpenoids: Part XC. A New Synthesis of Methyl Ether of Bakuchiol

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1-(Tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy) pentan-4-one (VI), prepared from laevulinic ester, reacts readily with ethyl α -diethylphosphono acetate in the presence of NaH to provide ethyl 3-methyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy)-2-hexenoate (VII) which is reduced with LAH to the corresponding alcohol (VIII). (VIII) on transformation into its allyl vinyl ether (IX) and subsequent thermal rearrangement produces aldehyde (X). Grignard reaction of *p*-methoxyphenyl magnesium bromide on the aldehyde (X) yields carbinol (XI) which upon dehydration with POCl₃ in pyridine provides 1-*p*-(methoxyphenyl)-3-methyl-3-vinyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy) hexene (XII). (XIII), procured by the hydrolysis of (XII) with PTS, gives the aldehyde (XIV) on CrO₃-Py oxidation. Finally, the Wittig reaction of isopropylidene-triphenylphosphorane on (XIV) furnishes the title compound (I).

SUKHDEV and coworkers isolated a phenolic terpenoid (C₁₈H₂₄O) from the seeds of *Psoralea corylifolia* Linn¹ and named it Bakuchiol. Structure (II) was assigned for it on the basis of chemical reactions and spectral data. Further confirmation of the structure (II) was provided by a synthesis of its methyl ether (I)².

In the present communication, we wish to report a new synthesis of the methyl ether of bakuchiol by

a different approach in which the olefinic bonds have been created through Wittig reaction and Claisen rearrangement. The sequence of reactions employed is given here.

The starting material, the ketal carbinol (IV), was obtained from laevulinic ester by ketalization followed by LAH reduction. The ketal carbinol (IV) was deketalized with dil HCl in acetone to keto-carbinol (V) which was transformed into its tetrahydropyranyl ether (VI) with dihydropyran³ in the presence of catalytic amounts of HCl. Modified Wittig reaction with ethyl α -diethylphosphonoacetate⁴ on ketone (VI), using NaH as a base and diglyme as a solvent, furnished α , β -unsaturated ester (VII). LAH reduction of (VII) in ether yielded allylic alcohol (VIII) which was converted into its allyl vinyl ether (IX) through equilibration with ethyl-vinyl ether in the presence of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate⁵. Pyrolysis⁶ of purified (IX) in a sealed tube under nitrogen atmosphere generated the aldehyde (X) in good yield. This was subjected to a Grignard reaction with *p*-methoxyphenyl magnesium bromide to produce carbinol (XI) which was subsequently dehydrated to (XII) under mild conditions using POCl₃ in pyridine⁷ at low temperature. Treatment of the pyranyl ether (XII) with PTS in methanol⁸ resulted in the formation of carbinol (XIII) which was smoothly oxidised with Collin's reagent⁹ at room temp. to give 4-methyl-4-vinyl-6-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-5-hexen-1-al (XIV) in a 65.5% yield. Finally, the aldehyde (XIV) was submitted to Wittig reaction with isopropylidene-triphenylphosphorane to provide the methyl ether of bakuchiol (I) in good yield. Identity of the synthetic product was substantiated by I.R. and N.M.R. spectra.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded with Perkin-Elmer infracord 337 with

Beckmann I.R. 5 spectrophotometer, as thin liquid film using sodium chloride optics. N.M.R. spectrum was determined in CCl_4 using T.M.S. as an internal standard at 60 MHz.

4,4-Ethylenedioxy pentanol (IV)

This ketal-alcohol was prepared exactly according to the conditions laid down in the literature¹⁰ in a 80% yield, b.p. $115^\circ\text{--}17^\circ/5\text{--}6$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4565. Lit.¹⁰ reports η_D^{25} 1.4570.

I.R. spectrum showed peaks at 3375, 2920, 1450, 1380, 1330, 1260, 1230, 1140, 1070–1050, 955, 920, 855 and 790 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 57.70; H, 9.40. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 57.51; H, 9.65%).

4-Keto pentanol (V)

The ketal-alcohol (IV, 14.60 g) was mixed with *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (10.8 g), acetone (1810 ml) and water (99 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hr at room temperature and thereafter the excess of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid was destroyed by washing it with a 5% solution of sodium carbonate (saturated with sodium chloride). Acetone was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent distilled off. The residual material upon distillation under reduced pressure furnished the keto-alcohol (V) in 68.5% yield, b.p. $97^\circ\text{--}100^\circ/7$ mm γ_{max} 3400, 2950, 1715, 1450, 1380, 1325, 1260, 1230, 1140, 1050, 945, 920 and 855 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 58.35; H, 9.42. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 58.80; H, 9.87).

1-(Tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy)-pentan-4-one (VI)

A cooled mixture of keto-alcohol (V, 10.0 g) and dihydropyran (10.8 g) was treated with hydrochloric acid (2 drops) and then the contents were kept at 25° for 30 hr. Therefore, the product was extracted with ether, washed with potassium hydroxide solution, water and dried. Vacuum distillation gave the pyranyl ether (VI, 14.0 g) in a 77% yield, b.p. $115.20^\circ/10$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4976. γ_{max} 2940, 2750, 1715, 1460, 1440, 1410, 1350, 1315, 1280, 1260, 1205, 1190, 1165, 1142, 1128, 1080, 1040, 1025, 995, 910, 875 and 820 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 64.75; H, 9.98. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 64.49; H, 9.74%).

Ethyl 3-methyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy)-2-hexenoate (VII)

To sodium hydride (3.84 g) in diethylene glycol, dimethyl ether (50 ml) was added dropwise below 20° ethyl α -diethyl phosphonoacetate (18.0 g) with stirring and the solution was stirred until the gas evolution had ceased. To the resulting yellow solution was then added slowly the keto-ether (VI, 12.4 g). After the addition, stirring was continued for 3 hr and left overnight. It was warmed for 30 min at 60° , cooled and decomposed with ice-cold water. The product was extracted with ether and dried. Removal of the solvent and distillation of the residue afforded the unsaturated ester (VII, 11.5 g) in a 67.5% yield, b.p. $155^\circ\text{--}60^\circ/7\text{--}10$ mm. γ_{max} 2950,

1720, 1660, 1450, 1400, 1370, 1330, 1300, 1275, 1235, 1210, 1195, 1160, 1135, 1110, 1085, 1080, 1045, 995, 970, 915, 885 and 825 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 66.00; H, 9.25. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 65.59; H, 9.44%).

3-Methyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy)-2-hexenol (VIII)

To a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.94 g) in dry ether (150 ml) was added with stirring the α , β -unsaturated ester (VII, 5.0 g) in anhydrous ether (15 ml). After the addition was over, the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hr at 40° (bath temperature). After cooling the reaction mixture was decomposed with sodium potassium tartrate solution (20%) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried and the solvent expelled. The residual oil was distilled under vacuum to afford the allylic-alcohol (VIII, 3 g) in a 71.4% yield, b.p. $145^\circ\text{--}50^\circ/7\text{--}8$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.5180. γ_{max} 3430, 2950, 1660, 1460, 1440, 1375, 1350, 1330, 1280, 1265, 1250, 1205, 1190, 1160, 1145, 1125, 1080, 1030, 990, 970, 910, 880, 850, 820 and 750 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 67.12; H, 10.56. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.25, H, 10.35%).

3-Methyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy)-2-hexen-1-vinyl ether (IX)

A solution of allylic alcohol (VIII, 10 g) and freshly crystallised mercuric acetate (0.9 g) in ethyl vinyl ether (200 ml) was heated under gentle reflux for 10 hr. The contents were chilled in ice and stirred with a cold solution of sodium carbonate (75 ml, 10%) for 30 min. The organic phase was separated and dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. Evaporation of the solvent and chromatography of the residue over alumina using petroleum ether ($40^\circ\text{--}60^\circ$) as eluent gave the vinyl ether. This was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to afford (IX, 8 g) in a 71.4% yield, b.p. $135^\circ\text{--}40^\circ/10$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.5160. γ_{max} 3110, 2940, 1640, 1610, 1470, 1450, 1380, 1350, 1325, 1290, 1270, 1210, 1165, 1145, 1130, 1082, 1035, 995, 975, 910, 890, 875, 820 and 765 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 70.25; H, 10.35. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 69.96; H, 10.07%).

3-Methyl-3-vinyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy)-hexanal (X)

The allyl vinyl ether (IX, 9 g) was heated for 45 min under nitrogen atmosphere in a fully immersed sealed tube in an oil-bath at 180° . After cooling, the product was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish (X, 7 g) in a 77% yield, b.p. $155^\circ\text{--}60^\circ/10$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.5272. γ_{max} 3090, 2950, 2740, 1725, 1650, 1625, 1470, 1460, 1390, 1360, 1330, 1270, 1210, 1190, 1145, 1130, 1080, 1040, 995, 975, 910, 880 and 820 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 70.23; H, 9.78. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 69.96; H, 10.07%).

1-(*p*-anisyl)-3-methyl-3-vinyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyraniloxy)-hexanal (XI)

To the Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (1.05 g) and *p*-anisyl bromide (7.7 g) in dry ether (100 ml), was added dropwise the aldehyde (X, 7 g) in dry ether (15 ml) with cooling and stirring.

The reaction mixture after stirring for another hour was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature and then refluxed on water-bath for 3 hr. The contents were cooled, decomposed with cold solution of ammonium chloride and worked up in the usual manner. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish the carbinol (XI, 5 g) in a 50% yield, b.p. 165°/10 mm, η_D^{25} 1.5290. γ_{max} 3450, 2980, 2950, 1660, 1610, 1500, 1475, 1450, 1400, 1365, 1330, 1300, 1255, 1210, 1190, 1145, 1125, 1082, 1040, 1005, 975, 910, 890, 875, 830, 790, 760 and 700 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 72.66; H, 9.47. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.38; H, 9.26%).

1-(*p*-anisyl)-3-methyl-3-vinyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyranyloxy)-hexene (XII)

Phosphorus oxychloride (2.5 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of the alcohol (XI, 4.5 g) in anhydrous pyridine (20 ml) kept at 0°. The contents were stirred for 2 hr at the same temperature and left overnight below 5°. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent expelled. The residual material was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina eluting with pet. ether to afford 1-(*p*-methoxy phenyl)-3-methyl-3-vinyl-6-(tetrahydro-2'-pyranyloxy)-hexene (XII, 2.3 g) in a 54.8% yield, b.p. 155°-60°/10 mm, η_D^{25} 1.5208. γ_{max} 3080, 2950, 1620, 1600, 1500, 1470, 1450, 1400, 1370, 1300, 1255, 1210, 1190, 1180, 1135, 1110, 1082, 1040, 1005, 975, 915, 880, 830, 765 and 700 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 76.75; H, 9.40. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 76.32; H, 9.15%).

4-Methyl-4-vinyl-6-(*p*-anisyl)-5-hexen-1-ol (XIII)

A mixture of (XII, 2.3 g), PTS (2 g) and methanol (20 ml) was heated for 2 hr. The product was extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed with dilute solution of sodium hydrogen carbonate and dried. The solvent was then evaporated and residue on distillation gave the alcohol (XIII, 1.24 g) in a 71.6% yield, b.p. 145°-50°/7-10 mm, η_D^{25} 1.5405. γ_{max} 3375, 3080, 2940, 1650, 1625, 1600, 1525, 1475, 1460, 1390, 1310, 1260, 1185, 1115, 1075, 1045, 1005, 980, 915, 830 and 770 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 78.50; H, 9.45. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 78.01; H, 9.00%).

4-Methyl-4-vinyl-6-(*p*-anisyl)-5-hexen-1-ol (XIV)

Chromium trioxide (3.5 g) was added to a stirred solution of (6.5 ml) of pyridine in dry methylene chloride (30 ml). The yellow coloured complex thus formed was stirred for 15 min at room temperature. To this was added the alcohol (XIII, 1.24 g) in (5 ml) of dry methylene chloride. A tarry black deposit separated immediately and this was further stirred for about 20 min. Thereafter, it was poured into ice-cold water and extracted with methylene chloride. The combined organic phase was dried (CaCl_2). The solvent was distilled off and the residue chromatographed over alumina using pet. ether (40°-60°) as

eluent. The product so obtained was distilled under reduced pressure to obtain the aldehyde (XIV, 0.8 g) in a 65.5% yield, b.p. 140°-45°/10 mm, η_D^{25} 1.5392. γ_{max} 3070, 2940, 2710, 1725, 1660, 1600, 1580, 1500, 1450, 1420, 1370, 1250, 1180, 1110, 1040, 1000, 975, 915, 825, 810 and 760 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 78.80; H, 8.45. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 78.65; H, 8.25%).

3,7-Dimethyl-3-vinyl-4-(*p*-anisyl)-1,6-octadiene (I)

Isopropylidene triphenylphosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (0.25 g, 50%) DMSO (2.5 ml), and isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (2.2 g), in DMSO (5 ml). To this added the aldehyde (XIV) (0.8 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (4 ml) with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and then poured into cold water. The organic layer was extracted with petroleum ether, washed with water and dried. The solvent was removed and residue left behind was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina and subsequent distillation under reduced pressure to furnish the methyl ether of bakuchiol (I; 0.6 g) in a 70.2% yield, η_D^{25} 1.5419. Lit. reports¹ η_D^{25} 1.5421. γ_{max} 3070, 2920, 1640, 1615, 1600, 1520, 1480, 1460, 1430, 1380, 1300, 1255, 1180, 1110, 1090, 1040, 1005, 980, 920, 855, 835, 820, 745, and 700 cm^{-1} .

NMR spectrum (CCl_4) showed signals at δ : 1.18 (s, 3H; tertiary $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.58-1.66 (6H, 2-vinyllic methyls), 3.72 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 4.80-5.95 (m, 4H, olefinic), 6.08, 6.16, (2H, olefinic), 6.80 (d, 4H, aromatic protons). (Found: C, 84.65; H, 9.75. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.39; H, 9.69%).

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